

Little Fixes for Big Stuff

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What happens when an institution does not have sufficient resources to carry out elaborate treatments on all of its collections? The conservation labs at Parks Canada are responsible for all the artifacts from 167 national historic sites and 44 national parks. That is a lot of artifacts compared to the number of conservation staff. The problem is compounded by the distances between the laboratories and the historic sites and parks. This paper presents the work that was done at five of the Parks Canada sites. The closest to our Winnipeg location is Sloops Cove in northern Manitoba. It's a three hour plane flight followed by a boat ride to get there from the Winnipeg laboratory. The other sites are in Alberta and British Columbia, about a 16 – 20 hour drive from Winnipeg. Only the grader at Kootenay Crossing is actually accessible by a paved road. All the others have varying degrees of accessibility.

The first project is the locomotive and tender located on an abandoned spur line on Field Hill in Yoho National Park. The locomotive is one of two Baldwin Moguls used to construct the Spiral Tunnel at Kicking Horse Pass. The pass is so steep that a figure-eight tunnel had to be cut into the mountainside to reduce the grade to the level where a team of locomotives could pull trains over the pass. Both the construction locomotives were narrow gauge. When the work was completed, all the rail lines out of the area were wide gauge, so this locomotive was run up a spur line and tipped off. Its sister locomotive is believed to be at the bottom of a local lake, but nobody knows for sure.

All of the interesting parts were removed from the locomotive. If the railway company did not remove the bell, name plate and gauges when the locomotive was abandoned, then the railway collectors have finished the job. The wood for the cab is also gone. It was probably removed intentionally because the beams and flooring for the tender are still extant. The site is accessed by a narrow, private access dirt road for rail crews working on a tunnel farther along the slope. An interpreted hiking trail also passes by the site, which means that there is some signage for the visitors who make the trek up from the valley floor.

I first visited the site in 1999 and as far as we understand, no conservation work had ever been done there. Both the locomotive and tender were partially covered with forest debris, mostly pine needles and moss. The wooden parts were in very deteriorated state. The worst damage was the loss of the boiler jacketing. Further investigation of the ground around the boiler revealed remains of asbestos insulation stained rusty red from the breakdown of the steel jacketing. The asbestos containment is still being reviewed. Remote location asbestos abatement can be a topic for another paper at a later date. So what could we do to help mitigate the corrosion of the remaining metal? We felt that reducing the time of wetting would go a long way to reducing the rate of deterioration. In other words, we decided to remove the debris that was covering the metal. This was accomplished with plastic spatulas, wooden cuticle sticks and nylon scrub brushes. Inside the tender, the debris was particularly deep and the bulk of it was shovelled out.

No coatings were applied. We felt that the coatings would have to be replaced in a timely fashion or their failure would accelerate the corrosion. It could not be guaranteed that there would be resources available to recoat in the future.

The second site is First Oil Well in Western Canada National Historic Site. The majority of the cultural resources are found in two narrow valleys within the boundaries of Waterton Lakes National Park in south-western Alberta. The access is by foot without a trail. The site is a series of oil well heads and miscellaneous oil rig equipment dating from 1901 to 1922. The well heads are in a good state of preservation because the oil is still rising in the pipes. Mother Nature is doing her own conservation here. Unfortunately, the other pieces of equipment are deteriorating. The vegetation has grown over and through many of the pieces. This site was also a candidate for an in-situ clean-up; however, vegetation cannot be removed in a national park without permission. This is where the cultural and natural aspects of the site come into conflict. However, since the trees are not first growth and the whole area is disturbed vegetation from the oil well operations, we were able to get the permission required. The vegetation was cleared manually and the debris of leaves, needles, and soil was brushed from the metal and wood. This maintenance is on a five year cycle as part of the monitoring protocol. It has gone through two cycles now and although the results are anecdotal they look promising.

The third site is Sloops Cove at Prince of Wales' Fort National Historic Site in northern Manitoba along the coast of Hudson Bay. It was a mooring area for the Hudson's Bay Company trading sloops which worked along the coast of Hudson Bay in the 18th century. Crew members and other workers chiselled their names and sometimes the date into the rock outcropping. Since that time, *Xanthoria elegans*, *Parmelia conspersa*, *Aspicilia casesiocrinerea*, *Rhizocarpon germinatum*, and *Leptogium saturninum* lichens have grown over the granitic rock obscuring the markings so they could not be adequately recorded. There were also concerns about the lichen damaging the rock. In 1998, a team of surveyors and archaeologists documented the site. Conservators were asked to clean the area prior to the recording. The site had a history of previous lichen removals making accurate dating by lichen growth impossible. Records indicate a caretaker used an unspecified biocide on the inscriptions in the 1960's so we estimate it will take another 30 years before the site has to be cleaned again.

In 1997, a dilute solution of o-phenyl phenol was applied to the lichen over the markings. Immediately after the conservators left the site, it was washed off by a rain squall making it ineffective. In 1998, the conservators arrived on the site one day before the archaeologists. The lichen was supposed to be black and brittle, but instead it was looking healthy. The weather was miserable, windy, pouring rain and 9 C. Fortunately, the water-saturated lichen was easily brushed off, not even leaving a stain on the rock. The majority of the lichen mass came off with nylon and natural bristle brushes designed for washing floors. The lichen in the grooves was removed with a nylon bathroom grout brush which is quite narrow. Stubborn pieces of lichen in small pits were picked out with wooden cuticle sticks. It turns out that lichen relaxes its hold on the rock when it is wet. The next day the rain had stopped and the dry lichen was clinging tenaciously to the rock. It was found that soaking the lichen with water for about 30 minutes softened it to the point where it could be taken off using the techniques from the previous day. This technique has been tried successfully at two other national historic sites operated by Parks Canada. However, there are situations where it is not appropriate. Pigments in painted images may be damaged. Other lichen and rock combinations may not respond as well to the water. The work requires individuals with good hand skills who can assess the process and if necessary stop cleaning before mechanical damage occurs. This method may not work for every situation but, it is worth investigating because it is quick, simple, and environmentally friendly. Parks Canada is always looking for environmental friendly techniques for in-situ treatments because the application of potentially toxic chemicals at parks and historic sites is restricted, particularly in a riparian zone such as the cove.

The fourth situation was the road grader on display at Kootenay Crossing in Kootenay National Park in eastern British Columbia. The grader along with the fresno and slip were used in the construction of the

Banff-Windermere Highway from 1910 to 1923. When conservators first saw the grader in 1999, it was in poor condition. The wood was rotting and the paint layers were deteriorated. As part of an outdoor display, resources were found to fund a stabilization and coating project. The original paint was faded so samples were sent for analysis to the Conservation Sciences Branch of Parks Canada to determine the original colour scheme. We thought we were dealing with yellows. When the analysis came back as green, we were surprised and sent in another set of samples. Using Fourier transform infrared spectrophotometry, they were able to determine that the composition of the paint was chrome yellow and Prussian blue. Over time the Prussian blue had faded leaving just the yellow. We were fortunate to have access to the analytical services otherwise the whole grader would have been painted variations of yellow.

In the summer of 2001, the grader was taken to a local workshop for treatment. We prefer to work indoors where we can control the temperature while the paint cures. Weather in the Rocky Mountains can be unpredictable. The loose paint was removed using air abrasion with slag grit and all the metal was painted with a primer and alkyd paint system. From experience with the cannon at Prince of Wales' Fort, we prefer to use simple paints with formulations for rusty metal. When working in field situations on large objects, it is difficult to clean the metal surfaces to the bright finish paint manufacturers recommend. The rust formulations work well with the less-than-perfect surface preparation we usually attain. We also avoid epoxy systems because they can be finicky with the weather conditions and are more toxic for the conservator. To stabilize the piece structurally, the punky wood was replaced and coated with tung oil. The grader was scheduled to be repainted on a five year cycle, but the resources were not available at the appropriate time. It has been repainted once in-situ in 2011.

The final example is a small compressed air locomotive from Bankhead in Banff National Park also in the Rocky Mountains. It is part of a coal mine and townsite complex that operated from 1903 to 1922. The locomotive is on display along an interpreted walking path. When the weather is dry, a work vehicle can be driven in along an old trail.

The locomotive has been through several cycles of wax coating using a method similar to coating outdoor sculptures. The metal is heated with tiger (large propane) torches and the molten wax blend is applied to the hot surface. Just like sculptures, the wax has to be reapplied cyclically. Unfortunately, the wooden pilot beams at the front and back of the locomotive are not as straight forward. The nearly one hundred years of exposure to the elements has rotted the wood. At some time in the future, resources will have to be found to replace the wood. In the meantime, measured drawings of the beams were made to at least record them. If the wood does not survive until it can be replaced, there will be drawings to use for the reproductions. It is preferable to preserve the original fabric of the artifact, but it is not always possible for large artifacts, particularly ones in remote locations.

Parks Canada does not have the resources to provide complex conservation treatments and indoor storage in controlled environments for all of the collections in its care. Sometimes difficult decisions have to be made that result in artifacts being left where they are found on a mountain side or on a distant coastline. Those artifacts still deserve care, but that care must reflect the realities of the location and the resources that are available.

